

A NOTE ON THE APPLICATION OF POTASSIUM FERRICYANIDE METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF REDUCING SUGARS IN CANE JUICE.

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The estimation of glucose (reducing sugar) is generally made by Fehling's method. Attempts have, however, been made to estimate glucose in cane juice by Cole's (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 723) 1% potassium ferricyanide method with slight modification and excellent comparative results with the Fehling's solution have been obtained with the clear sodium phosphate filtrate of cane juice.

EXPERIMENTAL.

To a cold solution of potassium ferricyanide (1%, 20 or 40 c.c.), caustic potash (5%, 5 or 10 c.c.) containing a drop of 1% methylene blue in a conical flask (200 c.c.) about half the volume of sugar solution to be titrated were added and the solution heated to boiling on a wire gauze over a flame. The flame was then lowered and the sugar solution added allowing a few seconds between each addition until the fluid was decolourised within 32 seconds after one shake in case of exact titration. With an excess of sugar solution it takes more time for the after-blueing to occur. The whole operation should be completed within 2-3 minutes.

Comparison of the standard solutions with 1% dextrose and lævulose (3%) is given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Standard solution.	Dextrose (E. P., 1%) reqd. for titration.	Lævulose (E. P. 1%) reqd. for titration.	Remarks.
Potassium ferricyanide solution (1%, 20 c.c.)	2 c.c.	2 c.c.	The mean result of 10
Fehling's solution (4 c.c.)	2 c.c.	2 c.c.	Readings tabulated

TABLE II.

Serial Nos.	Standard solution.	Cane juice reqd. for titration.	Vol. of lead sub-acetate filtrate reqd. for titration.	Vol. of sodium phosphate filtrate reqd. for titration
1 ^a	20 c.c. 1 % ferricyanide solution	2.70 c.c.	3.2 c.c.	3.20 c.c.
	4 c.c. Fehling's	3.20	...	3.20
2	20 c.c. Ferricyanide	3.70	3.7	3.80
	4 c.c. Fehling's	3.20	...	3.85

The estimation of reducing sugars with Fehling's as well as with ferricyanide solution has been carried out with over two hundred of cane juice samples for the last two years. The results in the case of the sodium phosphate filtrate compared very well with these two standard solutions. With ferricyanide solution, a difference of values in the cane juice and the sodium phosphate filtrate is often observed. For the comparison of the results, two standard solutions of equivalent strength were always taken.

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^a The mean result of 6 readings.
